

Risk and Protective Factors of Psychological Resilience among Adolescents in the Coastal Area of Kerala, India: A Scoping Review

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This scoping review explores the psychological resilience of adolescents in Kerala's coastal regions, focusing on vulnerabilities arising from environmental and socio-economic challenges. The study maps existing literature to identify resilience-related issues, risk and protective factors, and strategies for improvement. Using Arksey and O'Malley's five-step framework, it involved developing research questions, selecting and analyzing relevant articles, and synthesizing findings. Databases like PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar were searched using keywords such as "adolescent and resilience" and "cognitive adaptation." From an initial pool of 118 articles published between 2019 and 2025, 15 were selected based on inclusion criteria. Key findings highlight risks such as exposure to natural disasters, social isolation, and inadequate mental health resources. Protective factors include family support, peer connections, coping skills, and structured intervention programs. These findings underscore the importance of prioritizing resilience-building interventions to improve adolescents' mental health and ability to face adversities, urging policymakers and mental health professionals to develop targeted programs for this vulnerable demographic.

Keywords: Adolescents, psychological resilience, coastal Kerala, mental health, risk and protective factors

Adolescence serves as an important stage of development characterized by profound physical, psychological, and social changes that importantly form an individual's cognitive capacities, personality formation, and interpersonal skills (Yang, 2024). At this stage, adolescents undergo swift biological and emotional transformations that affect their mental well-being and social adaptation (Wu et al., 2020). Although many young people navigate this transition successfully, adolescence is widely recognized as an elevated-risk period for the development of psychological and psychiatric conditions (Schlack et al., 2021). Experiencing crises during this critical phase can interrupt psychosocial functioning and obstruct long-term developmental results (Mesman et al., 2021). However, adolescents' capacity to adapt varies widely depending on the support available to them, highlighting the importance of psychological resilience as a core developmental asset. Adolescents who have lower resilience levels frequently find it challenging to handle stress and difficult situations, leading to maladaptive emotional and behavioral responses that negatively affect their well-being (Hellström & Beckman, 2021). They are more exposed to stress-related consequences such as anxiety, depression, and other mental health problems (Mesman et al., 2021). Insufficient resilience has also been associated with involvement in risky behaviors,

including substance abuse and self-harm, as adolescents attempt to manage distress (Ntshalintshali & Maepa, 2025). Furthermore, low self-esteem and negative self-perception can foster feelings of hopelessness and worthlessness (Konaszewski et al., 2021). Adolescents lacking resilience frequently encounter difficulties in establishing and maintaining healthy relationships, which increases their likelihood of social isolation (Hellström & Beckman, 2021; Konaszewski et al., 2021).

Adolescence acts as a time that is both susceptible to challenges and filled with possibilities, and it offers an alternative opportunity for developmental reorientation, enabling individuals to cultivate competencies that support health, productivity, and social engagement (Murray & Xie, 2024). Consequently, it is a stage that demands both the ability to develop and the fundamental resources required for survival (Mesman et al., 2021). Adolescents undergo significant transformations not only physically but also socially and emotionally as they progress toward adulthood (Mastorci et al., 2024). Despite expectations of mature behavior, the teenage brain continues to evolve into early adulthood, influencing decision-making and emotional control (Konaszewski et al., 2021).

Throughout this transition, involvement from parents typically declines, independence rises, and interaction among family members often becomes less efficient (Bi & Wang, 2021). Simultaneously, adolescents spend more time with peers, seek social approval, and explore new interests (Mesman et al., 2021). Their development is shaped by a complex interaction of risk and protective factors, which collectively determine whether they adapt resiliently or become vulnerable to psychological distress (Bozzini et al., 2021).

Resilience acts as an active process that allows people to adjust positively in the face of difficulties, instead of running away from obstacles, and they tackle them with hope and practical coping methods (Waugh & Sali, 2023). Those with high resilience

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demonstrate enhanced self-sufficiency, flexibility, and optimistic perspectives when confronting difficulties (Dangmann et al., 2024). In terms of mental health, resilience refers to the capacity to sustain or regain psychological well-being when faced with stress (Blanke et al., 2022). Importantly, resilience is not an unchangeable quality but rather a flexible ability that can be enhanced through therapy, coping-skill development, and the establishment of supportive social networks (Kunzler et al., 2020). Adolescents who receive suitable guidance and support can cultivate resilience that fosters healthy adjustment and individual development (Ostaszewski, 2020).

In the context of India, especially in Kerala, young people living along the coast encounter unique environmental and social difficulties. The 570-kilometre-long coastline of Kerala is particularly susceptible to climate-related threats, including storm surges, intense rainfall, and rising sea levels, with around 300 kilometres of this coastline facing repeated risks (Sreelakshmi et al., 2024; Saikrishnan et al., 2024). These dangers interrupt everyday activities, impact livelihoods, and destabilize communities (Laino & Iglesias, 2024). In these areas, restricted availability of mental health care, constant encounters with disasters, and feelings of social isolation intensify the susceptibility of adolescents (Ann Philip & Veeramani, 2022). As a result, psychological resilience serves as an essential adaptive tool that allows individuals to manage difficulties effectively and bounce back from hardship (Ronen, 2021).

This scoping review intends to consolidate current literature on the psychological resilience of adolescents in the coastal regions of Kerala, India. It aims to outline the scope, diversity, and character of the existing evidence to gain a deeper understanding of how resilience evolves in situations marked by environmental risk and economic strain. Articles were located using databases including Scopus, Google Scholar, PubMed, and ResearchGate, emphasizing publications from 2019 to 2025 that discuss resilience in adolescents within disaster-prone or coastal areas in India and other regions.

Method

Search Process

In this study, a scoping review methodology has been used to get a

review of adolescents who have low psychological resilience. The scoping review is an approach for 'mapping' related literature in a field of importance. This is successful when the subject hasn't been thoroughly examined previously. By analysing the scope, range, and type of existing research, scoping reviews provide a summary of research findings. We have followed in this study Arksey and O'Malley's five-step method, which has the following procedures: developing a research question, choosing relevant literature, selecting a subgroup of literature for evaluation, charting data from selected publications, and summarizing and presenting the results. What is known about adolescence and psychological resilience was the broad research question. To search published and grey literature from 2019 to 2025, this current study used different arrangements of the keywords "adolescent and resilience" and "cognitive adaptation and motivation". The preliminary search formed 118 articles, and they were evaluated for inclusion using the following criteria: (1) included publication years from 2019 to 2025, (2) adolescents who have low psychological resilience, (3) the study's main objectives, and (4) articles in English. To search Google Scholar, PubMed, ResearchGate, and Scopus were used. In this study Peer-reviewed journal papers, conference presentations, and published and unpublished dissertations and theses were all used. The articles that duplicate, narratives, expert opinions, individual case-study articles, commentaries, and letters were excluded from the scoping review. Finally, 15 publications were selected that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria for this research study.

Results

Search Results

We studied the results of the 15 related articles on various aspects of adolescents who faced low psychological resilience because of the social, natural, and economic exploitations. The following articles are included in this study: seven literature reviews and four correlational studies: three qualitative, one longitudinal, one cross-sectional, one quantitative, and one casecontrol study, as summarized in Table 1. Some studies employed overlapping methodological designs; therefore, categories are not mutually exclusive.

Table 1
Summary of Review Articles based on the Scoping Review

Authors/date/country	Types of articles	Key aims/objectives
Bonanno et al., 2024, USA	Literature review	To broaden the field's perspective on resilience after disaster.
Fu & Zhang 2024, China	Systematic review	To study the impact of community-oriented programs in disaster education on the resilience and well-being of teachers.
Turgut Atak & Bebiş, 2024, Turkey	Systematic review	To recognize the risk factors (personal, familial, environmental) that adversely affect psychological resilience in adolescents living in institutional care.
Chulakarn & Chaimongkol, 2021, Thailand	Empirical, quantitative model-testing N=240	To test a connecting model of factors influencing resilience among institutionalized early adolescents, focusing on self-concept, coping, and school engagement.
Surzykiewicz et al., 2022, Poland	Quantitative, cross-sectional mediation N=251	To test whether self-esteem and perceived social support mediate the relationship between resilience and emotional regulation in adolescents
Guo & Liang, 2023, China	Empirical quantitative study N=818	To examine whether physical activity acts as a causal predictor of adolescent resilience
Wicaksono, 2021, Indonesia	Systematic literature review	To identify and synthesize internal and external factors that contribute to resilience
Ostaszewski, 2020, Poland	Editorial/viewpoint article	To emphasize the role of resilience in promoting adolescent mental health and preventing risk behaviours, highlighting key protective and strength-based factors for prevention programs.
Yang et al., 2023, Taiwan	Empirical quantitative research N=516	To examine how early environmental adversity affects cognitive ability, body mass, and life-history behavioral patterns in adults.

Lomeli-Rodriguez et al., 2025	Empirical qualitative research N=80	To explore how adolescents and their caregivers develop and express psychological resilience following exposure to disasters.
Mesman et al., 2021, Netherlands	Literature review	To give an enhanced summary of the latest clinical and epidemiological research on resilience and mental health among children and adolescents.
Prokosch et al., 2022, USA	Cross-sectional observational study. N=1307	To investigate the relationships among different social determinants of health (SDOH) and mental health outcomes for both parents and children in households that are diverse in terms of socioeconomic status and race/ethnicity, as well as to determine which SDOH are most closely associated with mental health issues in these families.
Liu & Chen 2025, China	Empirical/quantitative research article N=3710	Family economic adversity is important for expectant mental health. Stress process theory shows how stressors, particularly in the socioeconomic field, impair health and well-being.
Brandt et al., 2022, Germany	Narrative review	To synthesize evidence from basic (animal) and human research about how social isolation stress and discrimination affect mental health
Abate et al., 2024, Ethiopia	Umbrella review	To summarize global evidence on protective factors and interventions that strengthen resilience after adversity.

The following sections present the findings, which focus on the prevalence, impacts, risk, and protective factors of adolescents with low psychological resilience.

Risk Factors of Psychological Resilience among Adolescents

Natural Calamities

Catastrophic events like earthquakes and tsunamis are intense occurrences that can lead to psychological damage for the survivors (Bonanno et al., 2024). This damage may manifest as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), as well as depression and anxiety (Lomeli-Rodriguez et al., 2025). Natural calamities are unforeseeable and often have a significant impact, causing harm to human life and property in a brief period (Bonanno et al., 2024). Flooding is among the most common types of natural disasters worldwide (Fu & Zhang, 2024). Floods can be triggered by various factors, such as heavy rainfall, overflowing rivers, or tsunamis, and their consequences can be devastating, resulting in physical damage, loss of property, and, most importantly, significant psychological effects on affected individuals and communities (Bonanno et al., 2024). The emotional trauma resulting from natural disasters, like floods, is a serious issue that affects individuals' psychological and emotional well-being (Lomeli-Rodriguez et al., 2025). Emotions such as fear, anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress are some of the psychological effects that can manifest after experiencing a natural disaster (Bonanno et al., 2024; Lomeli-Rodriguez et al., 2025). Children and adolescents, who often struggle to deal with their post-disaster emotions and experiences, are the groups most susceptible to these psychological effects (Lomeli-Rodriguez et al., 2025). Catastrophes have the potential to happen suddenly and result in staggering levels of destruction (Bonanno et al., 2024). They can also develop gradually due to the spread of events or reasons that ultimately impact large segments of a population (Bonanno et al., 2024). The significant level of unpredictability that defines disasters, along with their extensive effects, can lead to various mental health outcomes, from overall distress to feelings of sadness, nervousness, sorrow, suicidal thoughts, or emotional trauma (Lomeli-Rodriguez et al., 2025). While much of the research on disasters has concentrated on severe psychological damage, there is also a significant and expanding body of literature that has recorded numerous instances of resilience (Bonanno et al., 2024). Resilient societies are more

equipped to endure and bounce back from disasters, resulting in reduced economic damage (Fu & Zhang, 2024). In terms of social aspects, resilient communities demonstrate greater social unity and confidence among residents, leading to a more effective reaction to emergencies (Bonanno et al., 2024). In terms of health, these communities frequently experience lower casualties and a swifter recovery to normal conditions after a disaster (Fu & Zhang, 2024). Children who are affected by disasters can develop increased fear, anxiety, and phobias and common fears among those who experienced a traumatic event are darkness, being alone, death, and the possibility of re-experiencing the event or a thought of a new trauma (Lomeli-Rodriguez et al., 2025). The memories of the traumatic event can bring distressing thoughts or images and that can make an individual feel helpless, hopeless, and fearful (Bonanno et al., 2024). The children who suddenly lose homes, schools, friends, and relatives manifest grief reactions like crying, sadness, depression, separation anxiety, and restlessness (Lomeli-Rodriguez et al., 2025; Bonanno et al., 2024). Children experience intense feelings of guilt and shame when a traumatic event is caused by the death of others and their survival (Bonanno et al., 2024).

Lack of Support

Adolescents require appropriate family and environmental conditions to foster their physical, mental, social, emotional, and moral development (Turgut Atak & Bebiş, 2024). When adolescents lack a supportive family, experience inadequate care, or are forced to live in unsuitable conditions due to poverty, migration, war, or other challenges, the state or charitable organisations may provide temporary or permanent protection (Chulakarn & Chaimongkol, 2021). The intervention helps safeguard them from negative circumstances, social and psychological risks, neglect, and abuse (Turgut Atak & Bebiş, 2024). In other terms, adolescence is a stage where possible crisis scenarios arise in biological, social, or familial contexts (Surzykiewicz et al., 2022). Children and adolescents are placed in the foster care system for various reasons, including the loss of one or both parents, abandonment due to family poverty, exposure to domestic violence, physical or sexual abuse, neglect by their families, or having a disability or mental illness. Although these circumstances represent significant and stressful events in the lives of young people, being removed from their homes often leads to feelings of confusion, anxiety, guilt, rejection, and abandonment (Chulakarn & Chaimongkol, 2021). Adolescents with a lack of

resilience can have delayed mental and social development, and also lack independence and responsibility, which can end up in game addiction, excessive anxiety, academic pressure, and other symptoms, later the individual can fall into depression, negative coping, suicide, poor academic performance, and other problematic behaviors (Guo & Liang, 2023). Overall, social support positively influences the alleviation of personal psychological stress, the management of negative feelings, the reinforcement of positive emotions, and the enhancement of mental well-being (Surzykiewicz et al., 2022).

Mental Health Issues

Research continuously indicates that fewer mental health issues are linked to better resilience levels (Mesman et al., 2021). The World Health Organisation highlights the significance of mental health among adolescents, noting that over fifty per cent of all mental disorders start during the adolescent years (Guo & Liang, 2023). Victims of Adverse Childhood Experience (ACE) can develop additional harmful stress because of their trauma, such as liver disease, cancer, ischemic heart disease, chronic lung disease, and skeletal fractures (Abate et al., 2024). Experiencing difficulties during childhood, having a parent with mental health issues, being bullied, and facing major threats are recognised risk factors that can lead to the emergence of mental health disorders in children and adolescents (Mesman et al., 2021). Exposure to Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) can increase the likelihood of a range of health and social issues, such as abuse, sexually transmitted infections, as well as complications related to maternity and pediatric health (like teenage pregnancy, pregnancy-related issues, & fetal mortality), human trafficking, suicide, and long-term illnesses including diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and cancer (Abate et al., 2024). Adolescents with poor environmental adaptability tend to adopt immature defence mechanisms, such as depression, withdrawal, avoidance, and anger, among others, when stressful events occur (Guo & Liang, 2023). Additionally, it is a period when young individuals are more susceptible to mental health issues such as depression, suicidal tendencies, eating disorders, substance abuse, and other addictive behaviours (Ostaszewski, 2020).

Economic Instability

Economic adversity directly increases an individual's risk of mental health. (Liu & Chen, 2025). Anxiety and mental distress are strongly linked to social vulnerability. A significant factor contributing to disparities in mental health is the unequal access to social determinants of health, including low levels of education, inadequate educational resources, and educational inequalities; instability in housing, substandard housing conditions; as well as unemployment, underemployment, and job insecurity (Prokosch et al., 2022). The circumstances in which a person lives play a role in the likelihood of developing a mental illness (Liu & Chen, 2025).

Social Alienation

Social exclusion and isolation are major causes of emotional distress (Chulakarn & Chaimongkol, 2021). These issues are linked to many mental health problems, including mood disorders like depression, psychosis, and substance abuse (Mesman et al., 2021). Feeling alone or left out can worsen mental health, highlighting how important community support and inclusion are in reducing these risks (Brandt et al., 2022).

In settings like institutions and coastal communities, a lack of robust social connections and feelings of marginalization can increase the risk of mental health issues (Chulakarn & Chaimongkol, 2021). Adolescents experiencing alienation frequently report increased anxiety, low motivation, and reduced academic engagement, which in turn perpetuate feelings of helplessness (Mesman et al., 2021). Kids might be especially susceptible because of the enduring impacts of social isolation and the stress of discrimination on their developing brains (Brandt et al., 2022).

Protective Factors of Psychological Resilience among Adolescents

Internal Factors

Internal factors, or those that originate from within a person, like their emotions, play a part in determining their resilience (Wicaksono, 2021). Resilience refers to the dynamic and adaptive process of maintaining or restoring mental health in the face of stressors, which may include trauma, difficult life situations, major transitions, or physical illnesses (Surzykiewicz et al., 2022). The development of resilience following adversity can be enhanced by protective factors and the use of interventions that encourage resilience (Wicaksono, 2021). Therefore, it is crucial to explore protective factors to mitigate the adverse effects of negative life events and to strengthen resilience through constructive risk-response strategies (Abate et al., 2024).

External Factors

External factors, including familial relationships, significantly influence an individual's level of resilience (Turgut Atak & Bebiş, 2024). These external influences play a crucial role in shaping how one responds to challenges and adversity (Wicaksono, 2021). This involves bolstering financial assistance for households, advocating for violence prevention measures, ensuring the healthy development of young children, improving parenting techniques and resilience skills for youth, nurturing supportive connections, and offering prompt interventions (Abate et al., 2024). Numerous studies and related research indicate the significance of fostering resilience across various fields (Wicaksono, 2021; Ostaszewski, 2020; Abate et al., 2024; Bonanno et al., 2024). In the realm of education, research highlights the importance of social support, emotional intelligence, and resilience among special schoolteachers, as well as their impact on thesis completion and academic performance (Ostaszewski, 2020; Surzykiewicz et al., 2022). In the health sector, evidence shows that resilience can enhance the physical health of individuals living with HIV and advanced breast cancer, and it can also facilitate the recovery process during drug rehabilitation (Wicaksono, 2021). Studies show that adolescents who thrive in supportive settings exhibit enhanced self-regulation and are less vulnerable to anxiety and depression. Conversely, a lack of supportive social frameworks is frequently linked to reduced resilience. Therefore, the existence of robust external support networks acts as a protective measure, bolstering adolescents' ability to bounce back from difficulties and adjust to unfamiliar situations.

Behavioural Factors

From a health perspective, adolescence is among the healthiest phases in life (Bonanno et al., 2024). It represents a time of maximum vitality and physical strength (Mesman et al., 2021).

However, concurrently, this stage is characterised by an increased propensity for engaging in risky behaviors that jeopardise the health and well-being of adolescents (Bonanno et al., 2024). Research has demonstrated that participating in physical activity can enhance the emotional well-being of adolescents, helping to convert feelings of anxiety, depression, and stress into positive emotions like happiness, joy, and relaxation (Guo & Liang, 2023). Therefore, adolescents who are not physically active may be more prone to adverse psychological problems (Bonanno et al., 2024). At the same time, adolescents who are severely lacking in physical activity are less able to resist the pressure around them, and are prone to depression, anxiety, loneliness, and decreased happiness (Ostaszewski, 2020). Enhancing relationships between teachers and students is linked to improved academic performance, greater engagement in prosocial activities, improved mental health, and reduced risk behaviors (Bonanno et al., 2024). The quality of the relationships between students and teachers is a crucial element of a positive school environment and students' attachment to their school. These supportive factors related to school enable students to build connections with their peers and more readily adjust to social norms and expectations (Guo & Liang, 2023). Together, these behavioural patterns serve as protective shields that assist adolescents in overcoming developmental challenges with enhanced confidence and psychological resilience.

Psychological Factors

Maturing is a crucial phase in human existence (Mesman et al., 2021). Because of uneven physiological and psychological growth, adolescents frequently encounter issues linked to mental well-being, adjustment, and perception, and they confront various developmental hurdles and responsibilities associated with family dynamics, relationships with peers, or their education (Surzykiewicz et al., 2022). Several elements contribute to fostering resilience (Turgut Atak & Bebiş, 2024). The length of difficult situations, the availability of supportive connections, and previous encounters with difficulties all impact a child's ability to be resilient (Chulakarn & Chaimongkol, 2021). The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention has identified approaches to reduce both the immediate and long-lasting effects of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs). These strategies involve increasing economic assistance for families, advocating for violence prevention measures, promoting the well-being of young children, improving parenting practices and youth resilience, cultivating supportive relationships, and delivering timely interventions (Abate et al., 2024). Early environmental adversities, encompassing experience of and exposure to violence, abuse, and neglect, may result in substantial neurobiological and cognitive consequences (Mesman et al., 2021). The research demonstrated that adolescents with improved cognitive flexibility, the capability to adjust their thinking and recontextualise difficulties, exhibited increased resilience and emotional stability when dealing with stress (Surzykiewicz et al., 2022). Improving their ability to think flexibly and solve problems was found to boost their ability to handle challenges effectively (Yang et al., 2024). The study found that internal motivation, self-esteem, and social support significantly enhance resilience among adolescents in institutional care, while stress and low self-worth reduce adaptive capacity.

Discussion

This scoping review lists accessible data concerning the psychological resilience of adolescents living in the coastal area of

Kerala, India, where constant issues like environmental, economic, and social challenges affect their resilience. Using Arksey and O'Malley's framework, the review organized empirical, theoretical, and review-based studies to pinpoint the risk and protective factors that influence adolescent resilience. The results show that resilience is not a fixed trait. Instead, it is a dynamic process that changes based on different contexts. Various factors, such as family, community, school, and the broader social environment, all shape resilience (Bonanno et al., 2024; Mesman et al., 2021).

In coastal Kerala, adolescents face specific challenges. They deal with frequent natural disasters, job insecurity, social isolation, and a lack of mental health services (Ann Philip & Veeramani, 2022; Saikrishnan et al., 2024). Stressful situations can lead to chronic stress and reduce a person's ability to cope. However, having protective factors like strong family relationships, support from friends, good coping skills, and participation in school activities can help lessen these effects. This support allows adolescents to maintain their mental health even during tough times (Surzykiewicz et al., 2022; Guo & Liang, 2023).

Research shows that resilience comes from a mix of personal strengths and support from others. Personal traits like optimism, self-esteem, and the ability to adapt help build resilience (Yang et al., 2023). At the same time, external support like being included in social groups, having a stable community, and participating in education also play important roles (Wicaksono, 2021). Most of the evidence comes from studies that look at a single point in time or show connections between things. This means we don't fully understand how resilience develops over time. Also, there are not enough intervention models that fit the culture of Kerala, which makes it hard to apply global findings to the local context.

A key point from this review is that building resilience should go beyond helping individuals. It should include community and systemic strategies. This means adding resilience education in schools, supporting family relationships, and ensuring government disaster plans focus on mental health recovery as well as infrastructure. While Kerala's State Disaster Management Plan identifies youth as an important group, it mainly focuses on physical infrastructure rather than mental health. Adding mental health programs and efforts to build resilience can help improve community readiness (Laino & Iglesias, 2024).

Resilience should be seen as a matter of social justice. It is important to recognize that inequalities related to gender, caste, and socioeconomic status affect adolescents' access to resources and their ability to cope. We need to move from a focus on problems to a focus on strengths. This means prioritizing empowerment, agency, and inclusion in resilience strategies. This change aligns with modern resilience theory, which treats adaptation as both a psychological and social issue.

Limitations and Future Directions

This review has several important limitations. It only included articles published in English from 2019 to 2025, which may have left out relevant studies in Malayalam or other languages. The studies used different designs, including qualitative and quantitative methods, making it hard to compare their results directly. Most of the studies relied on self-reported information and did not use standardized tools to measure resilience. This reduces the reliability and generalizability of the findings.

One issue is that most studies on resilience and mental health are cross-sectional. This means they provide a snapshot in time, which makes it hard to determine causes and effects. There is also a lack of studies that follow people over time or test specific interventions, limiting our understanding of how resilience grows. Many resilience-building programs come from outside India, which raises questions about how well they fit the local culture. Additionally, important demographic factors like gender, caste, socio-economic status, and disability are often overlooked, even though they significantly affect adolescents' psychosocial experiences.

Future studies should focus on long-term and experimental research to understand how resilience develops in teenagers facing difficult situations. It is important to create tools for measuring resilience that fit the culture and language of Kerala. This will help make research more comparable. Researchers should also look into programs like the Cognitive Adaptation and Motivation Program (CAMP) that can improve emotional control, coping strategies, and problem-solving skills in adolescents.

We need to focus on community-based strategies that involve families, teachers, religious groups, and local organizations. Including resilience training in school programs and disaster preparation can help people learn how to cope effectively and support long-term mental health. Future research should look at how factors like gender, caste, and economic differences affect resilience and outcomes.

Collaboration among psychologists, educators, policymakers, and public health professionals is crucial for creating effective programs that promote mental health while also reducing disaster risks. By working together, these groups can ensure that efforts to build resilience are based on solid science and fit the local culture. This approach can ultimately improve the ability of teenagers in Kerala's coastal areas to adapt to challenges.

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